

Assessing QoE in Edge-Delivered Holographic Streaming with a Programmable Hardware Testbed

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Abstract—Holographic-type communication demands multi-Gbps throughput and ultra-low latency, posing significant challenges to current 5G networks. This demo work presents a programmable testbed built on the P7 network emulator, which overcomes the throughput constraints of conventional platforms. Our demonstration deploys three edge computing slices—one at a far edge and two at near edges—to support volumetric media streaming directly to VR head-mounted display. By facilitating precise adjustment of network metrics such as latency and packet loss across the P7-enabled slices, the testbed allows users to visually observe the resulting effects on holographic content in VR. Although automated measurement of Quality of Experience (QoE) parameters are not incorporated, the testbed provides a valuable experimental environment where researchers can subjectively evaluate the relationship between network conditions and perceived quality, thereby gaining insights into optimizing network performance for enhanced Quality of Service (QoS).

Index Terms—HTC, volumetric, P7, QoS, QoE.

I. INTRODUCTION

Immersive technologies (e.g., virtual reality, multisensory extended reality) are changing digital interactions, with Holographic-type Communications (HTC) [1] evolving as a specially demanding kind of application. Transmitting holographic/volumetric content, including Point Clouds (PCs) and Light Fields (LFs), with six degrees of freedom (6DoF) requires massive bandwidth (Gbps to Tbps) and ultra-low latency (<5 ms), which is beyond the capabilities of current 5G networks, leading to increased research on 6G systems.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as peak data rate, user-experienced data rate, and latency are vital metrics for evaluating HTC systems [2], with latency being particularly critical for PC transmission. To meet these KPI demands, next-generation networks must leverage Software Defined Networks (SDNs) for flexible and programmable network management and Network Function Virtualizations (NFVs) to virtualize network functions. Additionally, network slicing optimizes resource allocation per application, while edge computing reduces latency by processing data closer to users. These technologies collectively minimize Quality of Service (QoS) degradation, enhancing the Quality of Experience (QoE) for immersive applications.

To enable practical experimentation with cutting-edge technologies, the P4 Programmable Patch Panel (P7) [3] serves as a high-fidelity hardware-based network emulator by allowing researchers to conduct experiments on a single high-performance

programmable platform. P7 can instantiate network elements, create multiple switch instances of custom P4 codes, generate background traffic, define link characteristics such as bandwidth, latency, packet loss, and jitter, and implement network slices. It can emulate distributed edge computing environments through emulated switches and links, which makes it particularly valuable for HTC research, as it facilitates precise modeling of multi-tiered edge architectures while delivering 100 Gb line-rate throughput.

While the potential of SDN/NFV for holographic communication has been explored [4] [5], existing research often lacks a comprehensive evaluation of actual volumetric media transmission and real immersive Virtual Reality (VR) experiences. Moreover, existing network emulation platforms, such as Mininet with behavioral model version 2 (bmv2), are still limited in throughput (at around 1 Gbps) [6], restricting scalable experimentation with HTC’s high bandwidth requirements. Although studies have investigated QoS’s impact on QoE for Head Mounted Display (HMD) users [7], they often do not fully leverage the benefits of a programmable network.

To address these gaps, our earlier work [8] demonstrated a P7-based programmable network testbed to showcase the impact of QoS on holographic streaming QoE. This work leverages our earlier work by introducing network slicing and edge computing concepts into the testbed for holographic streaming. This demonstration features a P7-based programmable testbed to create three distinct network slices across edge computing regions (one far edge and two near edges) supporting holographic volumetric streaming. The dynamic adjustment of latency and packet loss across P7-enabled slices will be observed in real-time to assess how it impacts the QoE of users wearing HMD while interacting with immersive VR holographic content.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

A. Programmable Testbed

Our testbed environment for holographic streaming employs P7 on top of a programmable switch to enable data plane functionality through P4 programs and realistic emulation of complex network topologies. The implementation architecture, as illustrated in Figure 1, comprises six emulated switches, Sw1, Sw2, Sw3, Sw4, Sw5, and Sw6 that connect

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed programmable testbed.

the end user to the service edges. It is worth mentioning that the topology and the metrics can be updated at runtime.

The network is configured to support three distinct service tiers implemented as network slices with progressively degraded QoS parameters: Slice 1 constitutes a high-performance tier with minimal network impairment (labeled Optimal), Slice 2 provides an intermediate service level (labeled Average), and Slice 3 represents a degraded network condition (labeled Poor). The links between switches are configured by P7 according to a specific server port requested by the VR application, dynamically switching between these slices. The demonstration focuses on two critical QoS metrics: latency and packet loss. Latency values are configured at 0 ms for Slice 1, 5 ms for Slice 2, and 10 ms for Slice 3, while packet loss is maintained at 0% for Slices 1 and 2, increasing to 1% for Slice 3 to simulate network congestion effects.

To support the delivery and processing requirements of volumetric streaming in VR HMD, the testbed incorporates a multi-tier edge computing model in which network slices are mapped to far-edge and near-edge computing [9] tiers. Slice 1 is mapped to far-edge computing, which is generally located at the network periphery (e.g., cell sites) offering ultra-low latency capabilities, particularly suitable for real-time viewpoint rendering offloading. In contrast, both Slice 2 and Slice 3 operate within the near-edge computing domain, situated at network aggregation points or regional data centers where higher latency and variable QoS, but greater computational capacity, are anticipated than the far edge. Within this tier, Slice 2 represents a moderately impaired condition where services, such as content transcoding/caching, can still be performed reliably by maintaining a satisfactory user experience. Slice 3, also on the near edge, reflects further degraded conditions with increased latency and packet loss to represent scenarios where network congestion or resource contention limits performance. This multi-tiered approach optimizes the processing and delivery pipeline for holographic applications across different network slices. Another key aspect of our testbed is overcoming throughput limitations by enabling multi-Gbps performance while allowing real-time assessment of precise QoS metrics impacts on real VR user QoE. Although we use specific metrics for this demo, these values can be adapted and reconfigured at runtime, enabling test validation with P7.

B. Technical Specification

The Ubuntu 22.04 servers for the demo run Nginx, operating on a 16-core 64-bit processor with 64 GB RAM. The programmable switch is a 3.2 Tbps Wedge 100BF-32X Tofino, connected to the servers using 25 Gbit/s optical interfaces. At the user end, Wi-Fi connectivity is delivered with up to 840 Mbps. The Meta Quest 3 HMD features 110 degrees Field of View (FoV), 120 Hz refresh rate, 2064x2208 pixels resolution per lens, chipset *Qualcomm Snapdragon XR2 Gen 2*, GPU *Adreno 740*, 8GB RAM and *Horizon OS*.

Resources: In our implementation, we leveraged PC technology for holographic content delivery, using the Long Dress sequence from an open-access repository¹. This 300-frame sequence was recorded at 30 Frames per Second (FPS) with approximately 800k points per frame. To reduce the substantial bandwidth requirements of high-fidelity holographic media, we employed the Google’s Draco² codec. The rendering infrastructure was developed using the Unity engine, optimized specifically for HMD performance.

Application: On the client side, a Unity-based application runs on a Meta Quest-3 VR device in “Standalone” mode, with wireless connectivity. Received files are decompressed using Draco and translated into meshes that are stored in a buffer for rendering. The Visual Effect Graph system renders each point of the mesh as a tiny square, creating a three-dimensional surface when viewed collectively. Under ideal network conditions, the PC animation plays seamlessly as files are loaded and processed faster than they are displayed. When network conditions degrade, loading times increase, causing stuttering as the program waits for additional files to arrive.

III. DEMONSTRATION AND RESULTS

A. Demonstration Workflow

The demonstration is carried out following a specific volumetric streaming dynamic workflow as illustrated in Figure 2. The process begins with the GET Request with a specific port linked to one of the quality levels (Optimal, Average, or Poor) that the user wants to experiment with, triggered by the Unity user ①. The request then reaches the P7 ②, where the slice selection process begins (based on the port previously chosen by the user) and forwards it to the specific path provided by the linked emulated switches. After leaving the P7 pipeline ③, the request reaches one of the edge servers. There, the nginx server processes the request ④, chooses the specific encoded PC files and forwards them ⑤ back to the P7 ⑥, where the port and destination address of the receiving packets are parsed and re-enter the determined slice ⑦ fabric. Once the packets reach the user’s HMD in the compressed format ⑧, the Unity application decompresses them, and finally, the volumetric video is played in the immersive VR application ⑨. The user’s HMD captured throughput, using

¹<https://plenodb.jpeg.org/pc/8ilabs/>

²<https://github.com/google/draco>

Fig. 2: Point Cloud (PC) video transmission workflow.

the `antmonitor`³ tool **10**, is correlated to FPS values (the objective QoE metric of choice in **11**).

B. Demonstration Experience

At the start, the user is presented with a simple virtual environment resembling a photography studio, with three settings available to be configured through three buttons representing the three different transmission qualities and text input boxes. To showcase the impacts of each network slice QoS parameters on the immersive application QoE, the demonstration will use two screens: the first screen showing the P7 terminal depicting the current specifications and the dynamic modification of the network metrics; while the other screen will show the HMD volumetric media performance. For each quality, the dynamic PC will be performed for 30 seconds. This allows the user to assess the smoothness of the volumetric video at the same time the FPS metrics are exposed in the same immersive environment. The recorded demonstration video, which highlights the results, can be accessed in this link⁴.

Optimal Quality: By pressing the Optimal button in the immersive environment, the Unity application will send the GET request packet with the *Far edge* server port. P7 will enable the $Sw1 \rightarrow Sw2 \rightarrow Sw3 \rightarrow Sw5 \rightarrow Sw6$ slice links. In this slice configuration, the throughput reaches up to 150 Mbps, while the QoE stays at approximately 24 FPS.

Average Quality: Pressing the Average button triggers the P7 parsing the server port, in this case the *Near edge 1*, and enable the $Sw1 \rightarrow Sw2 \rightarrow Sw4 \rightarrow Sw5 \rightarrow Sw6$ slice links. Here, the peak throughput is 80 Mbps, 46.67% less than the Optimal quality. The objective QoE scores stabilize at 15 FPS, 62% the value of the previous score.

Poor Quality: As before, the P7 will parse the server (in this case the *Near edge 2*) port and enable the last slice: $Sw1 \rightarrow Sw2 \rightarrow Sw3 \rightarrow Sw4 \rightarrow Sw5 \rightarrow Sw6$ links. This slice introduced packet loss, therefore, the impact on the throughput was even greater. With maximum throughput of 40 Mbps, it

is 73.33% less than the Optimal slice, while the QoE metrics fall to 10 FPS, 41% of the Optimal quality.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this demonstration, we presented a programmable testbed using the P7 tool for fine dynamic adjustment of QoS metrics (latency and packet loss) to evaluate their impact on the user's HMD QoE through an immersive application. For future work, we plan to expand the emulated switches environment to enhance the combination of QoS metrics (latency, packet loss, and jitter) and subjective QoE, broadening the scope of volumetric media streaming research toward 6G.

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³<https://github.com/UCI-Networking-Group/AntMonitor>

⁴DEMO video:<https://tinyurl.com/netsoft25>